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BMD

Biodiversity Meets Data

MS28 First cycle of workshops with key-stakeholder meetings, in collaboration with WP1, completed

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Summary

This report provides an overview of the co-design activities comprising the first cycle of workshops with key stakeholders for the Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project from 2025 to 2026. The active collaboration with stakeholders is central to the design of the tools being delivered by BMD to support better biodiversity monitoring, conservation and restoration across Europe’s Natura 2000 sites. Detailed reports, thematic feedback databases and supplementary short co-design activity reports were produced following the completion of the first cycle of workshops and reflect on the key insights that emerged from the co-design activities. This report therefore provides a high-level overview of the stakeholder engagement activities completed to date, details how the contributions to these activities will shape the design and functionalities of the Single Access Point (SAP), and provides a brief outline of the co-design activities planned in the lead-up to Deliverable 6.1 (*Report on the key-stakeholder engagement, due February 2027*).

List of abbreviations

BAT	Biodiversity Analysis Tool
BMD	Biodiversity Meets Data
EU	European Union
MS	Milestone
SAP	Single Access Point
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

The Biodiversity Meets Data (BMD) project is mobilising an ethical, participatory and adaptive approach to delivering a Single Access Point (SAP) to high-throughput biodiversity data, monitoring and analyses that is co-designed in collaboration with stakeholders. Working closely with stakeholders to create the SAP and the underpinning Biodiversity Analysis Tools (BATs) is essential for ensuring that the tools delivered by BMD meet the needs and priorities of the stakeholders: namely, Europe's Natura 2000 site managers and policymakers. An iterative stakeholder engagement process is being implemented throughout the lifecycle of the project to enable stakeholder participation in the decision-making that shapes the design and functionalities of the SAP and underpinning BATs. Between 2025 and early 2026, BMD conducted stakeholder mapping (see Wooldridge et al., 2025a), produced a project-wide stakeholder engagement plan (see Wooldridge et al., 2025b), and maintained an adaptive approach to the ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. The first cycle of workshops and co-design activities was therefore facilitated based on these findings, methods and principles.

Detailed workshop reports were published on the project website following the completion of the first cycle of workshops in the 2025 to 2026 period (see Wooldridge 2025a & 2025b, and Wooldridge et al. 2025c). With this in mind, this report provides a brief overview of the co-design activities facilitated to date (Section 2 *Overview of Co-Design Activities Completed*) to support MS28 “*First cycle of workshops with key-stakeholder meetings, in collaboration with WP1, completed*”. The overview of co-design activities completed to date is followed by reflections on how the contributions to these activities feed into the design and delivery of the SAP (Section 3: *Incorporating Stakeholder Contributions into the SAP*). Finally, the next cycle of co-design activities planned in the lead up to Deliverable 6.1 (Report on the *key-stakeholder engagement, due February 2027*) are outlined (Section 4 *Next Steps*).

2. Overview of Co-Design Activities Completed

The first cycle of co-design activities with stakeholders was focused on increasing the visibility of the project with key stakeholder groups; on gathering broad feedback and initial impressions regarding the SAP and BAT concepts and mock-ups; and on conducting participatory workshops to understand and identify stakeholders' biodiversity data, monitoring and analysis needs. Table 1 provides an overview of the co-design activities implemented between 2025 and 2026. BMD worked closely with Eurosite to deliver co-design activities that showcased the BMD project and initiated the first opportunities for stakeholder participation in the co-design of the SAP and BATs at the early stages of their development. Many of the activities outlined in Table 1 invited stakeholders to provide their initial feedback and ideas relating to the SAP and BATs and enabled BMD to gather early insights into the types of tools and designs that might be most attractive and useful for Natura 2000 site managers. As indicated in Table 1, the feedback was recorded and reported in one or multiple of the following formats: co-design activity report (internal only), thematic feedback database (internal only), milestone report, or deliverable report.

Table 1: Overview of BMD Co-Design Activities 2025-2026

Activity Title	BMD Topic	Location	Date	N. Participants	Outputs*			
					A	B	C	D
User Story Workshop	BAT	Vilnius, Lithuania	September 2025	15	X	X	X	X
Showcasing & Feedback at BMD Booth	BAT	Vilnius, Lithuania	September 2025	16	X	X		X
Showcasing & Feedback at BMD Booth	SAP	Vilnius, Lithuania	September 2025	2	X	X		X
Remote Sensing & New Technologies Discussion	Plug-and-Play	Vilnius, Lithuania	September 2025	10	X			X
User Story Workshop	BAT	Umea, Sweden	September 2025	37	X	X	X	X
Showcasing & Feedback at BMD Booth	BAT	Umea, Sweden	September 2025	39	X	X		X
Showcasing & Feedback at BMD Booth	SAP	Umea, Sweden	September 2025	11	X	X		X
Plug-and-Play Discussion Forum	Plug-and-Play	Umea, Sweden	September 2025	29	X			X
User Story Workshop	BAT	Online	November 2025	19	X	X	X	X
SAP Mock-Up Viewer	SAP	Online	September 2025 - February 2026	14				X

* A = co-design activity report (internal only), B = milestone report, C = deliverable report, D = feedback database (internal only)

3. Incorporating Stakeholder Contributions into the SAP

While each co-design activity conducted to date focused on a specific element of BMD (BAT use cases, SAP interface preferences, Plug-and-Play device deployment), in combination, all stakeholder contributions will work to shape the overall outcome of the SAP, to ensure that it is designed in a way that is intuitive and useful for BMD stakeholders. The ways in which stakeholder contributions to date are shaping the SAP are highlighted below.

User Story Workshops: A list of 11 exemplary user stories was produced based on the contributions from the 57 stakeholders who participated in the in-person and online workshops (see Wooldridge et al. 2025c). These user stories encompass specific needs around biodiversity data, monitoring and analysis. These needs were highlighted through the participatory workshops that guided stakeholders in considering the biodiversity information needed to support their conservation and restoration work. The user stories provide the BMD technical teams with stakeholder-identified use cases, which inform the thematic direction of the BATs and ensure that the tools situated within the SAP meet the biodiversity data, monitoring and analysis needs of the stakeholders.

Showcasing & Feedback Booths (SAP): At an early stage of development of the SAP interface, the BMD team invited stakeholders to share their initial impressions of the SAP following a brief presentation of the SAP concept and its four visual mock-ups. Comments were recorded at the booths and later collated into an online database shared with the BMD team working on the design and delivery of the SAP. Comments were also gathered directly on the SAP mock-up viewer, enabling stakeholders to explore the different mock-ups, rank each design based on their own preferences and provide further details on the rationale behind their preferences.

Showcasing & Feedback Booths (BAT): To gather some initial feedback and ideas relating to the BATs, the BMD team showcased a demo version of a species distribution model at the booths and prompted discussion about the visual and functional elements that stakeholders might need to run their desired analyses. Comments were recorded at the booth and collated in an online database shared with the technical teams working to produce the BATs. Additionally, stakeholders were presented with a list of six terms that could be used to describe the BATs and were invited to vote for their preferred terminology.

Plug-and-Play Discussion Forums: As the SAP will provide both access to biodiversity information as well as a means to upload biodiversity information to open-source databases and for deployment of analytical tools, some initial use of plug-and-play devices is needed to start to drive this mobilisation of biodiversity information. In-person discussion forums were facilitated to present BMD's approach to supporting the deployment of plug-and-play devices by site managers, and to better understand stakeholders' familiarity with and intended use cases for the technologies being deployed (i.e. camera traps, eDNA sampling, audio moths). Contributions were recorded via MentiMeter, and stakeholders interested in deploying plug-and-play devices provided their contact details for further involvement in this particular element of BMD.

4. Next Steps

The first cycle of co-design activities between 2025 and 2026 has enabled stakeholder participation in the early design stages of BMD, and provided key insights into the biodiversity data, monitoring and analysis needs of Europe's Natura 2000 site managers and policymakers. Future co-design activities will invite stakeholders to further influence the design of the SAP interface and shape specific elements of the SAP, including: terminology, visual appearance and functional aspects. Similarly, at later stages of the project, stakeholders will be invited to test the SAP and BATs developed and provided focused feedback on these tools. In the lead-up to Deliverable 6.1 *Report on the key-stakeholder engagement (due February 2027)*, the following co-design activities will be facilitated, encompassing ongoing collaborations within the project and with stakeholders that are shaping the outcomes of BMD:

- Online webinars and Q&A sessions to facilitate dialogue between stakeholders and BMD technical teams (including those responsible for the delivery of the SAP, BATs & Plug-and-Play device deployment)
- Thematic focus groups to make collaborative decisions on the design of the SAP interface
- In-person workshops for training and capacity building to support the deployment of plug-and-play devices
- Polling on terminology preferences to identify a suitable and intuitive name for the SAP
- A final user story workshop to identify further use-cases for the BAT's and fill gaps in representation, particularly focusing on the marine and freshwater realms

5. References

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